

Peters, S. & Meyne, L. (2023). Motivation in international VET cooperation: VET providers and their engagement in transfer. In V. Tütlys, L. Vaitkutė & C. Nägele (Eds.), *Vocational Education and Training Transformations for Digital, Sustainable and Socially Fair Future. Proceedings of the 5th Crossing Boundaries Conference in Vocational Education and Training, Kaunas, 25. – 26. May* (pp. 349–354). European Research Network on Vocational Education and Training, VETNET, Vytautas Magnus University Education Academy, Institute of Educational Science. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7822041>

Motivation in International VET Cooperation: VET Providers and their Engagement in Transfer

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Abstract

This paper represents a first contribution in the context of international vocational training research on the side of German VET providers who want to transfer their VET services from Germany as the origin country to another target country and asks about the motivation to become active in this regard. Case studies are applied that involve German VET providers, sampled from a German funding line. In-depth expert interviews with six project actors are conducted to identify the perspectives and approaches for the motivation of transfer. Theoretical assumptions on motives and motivation of the Relationships Motivation Theory by Deci and Ryan, as well as the motives for policy transfer by Pilz and Li offer the analytical framework for this study. Although motives variate in many facets, two main motivations of the revenue-oriented motivation of transfer and the personal concerns motivation can be found according to the analysed data. Concluding, there are rather intuitive and interest-driven motives for engaging in transfer on the side of the analysed VET providers, which is why further research in this area would be desirable.

Keywords

transfer in VET, transfer in international vocational education and training, motivation for transfer, internationalization of VET, German VET provider

1 Context

In the context of international comparative Vocational Education and Training research, drivers and barriers to policy implementation are discussed as well as factors that significantly influence transfer processes at the level of political decision making. The existing state of research on the topic of VET transfer has so far been largely located at the macro level, although information on individual projects is useful in order to develop a better understanding of transfer, as their understanding in turn shapes the entire transfer work in the sector of VET. Therefore, we ask for the motivation to engage in transfer of vocational education and training service providers in internationalization projects.

Within the concomitant research of the funding line "Internationalization of Vocational Education and Training" (IBB) by the German federal ministry of education and research, we

accompanied 16¹ projects that aim at business model development of vocational education and training services as well as testing the implementation of these services in new markets. For example, one project of the funding cluster aims to sell welding certificates on the Brazilian market; another one intends to sell mechatronics courses to companies in Serbia. In this context, our research focuses on conducting qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys during different phases of the projects' funding as well as after project funding has ended. Therefore, in the context of this contribution, transfer is understood as educational transfer, meaning the transfer of VET structures, processes, contents and practices from an origin context to a target context (Frommberger & Baumann, 2019; Gessler, 2019). Gessler (2019) points out that in the context of VET transfer, several levels are always involved at the same time, more precisely those of "individuals, teams, institutions and systems" (p. 233). In the course of this study, the level of individuals (representing their organizations) is considered with regard to the concrete understanding of transfer in the cases analyzed. Our research question is: *How can the motivation regarding the transfer of VET providers participating in international projects for the development of business models for VET services be characterized?* Our analysis takes up results regarding the understanding of transfer and different levels of transfer (see Meyne & Peters, 2022) and has been part of the same research design and data collection.

2 Theoretical framework

Toepper et al. (2021) describe that "the role of individuals and the competence of instructors as well as other decision-makers is an important influencing factor" (Dowling et al., 2008; as cited in Toepper et al., 2021, p. 150) regarding VET transfer. Theoretical assumptions on motives and motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2008) offer the analytical framework for this context:

"In this way, it is clear that the policy lending approach is not a simple change in perspective from the receiving country to the transferring country. Instead, a distinction must also be made here between the motives for the transfer and the degree of voluntariness" (Pilz & Li, 2021, p. 7)

Deci and Ryan (2014) describe in their Relationships Motivation Theory (RMT) the relation between the quality of relationships and motivational dynamics. They state that those relationships are of high quality in which both partners experience autonomy. So, to what extent are motivation and voluntariness related to transfer? Deci & Ryan (1993, p. 225) state, "Self-determined and controlled behavior thus define the endpoints of a continuum that establishes the 'quality' or 'orientation' of a motivated action". We want to explore if the autonomy of project actors also has an influence on the outcome in project work. Here, it is important to see that we capture individual perspectives, not organizational ones.

3 Methods and sample

We use case studies that involve German VET providers, sampled from the German funding line "IBB". In total, the IBB funding line comprises 27 project proposals, including the concomitant research project of the entire funding line. Six projects from the funding cluster c "demand-oriented development and model implementation of education and training services for international markets" were analysed in the context of this study. The perspectives regarding the approaches to transfer are being collected in in-depth interviews with VET project actors.

¹ Those are projects from funding cluster c. The other two funding priorities relate to (a) 'bilateral exploratory projects on the prerequisites and topics of vocational training cooperation' and (b) 'measures to support and implement bilateral vocational training cooperation on a model basis', the IBB funding line comprises 27 projects in total.

The sample of our study was selected based on the most-different-system design, so that the projects analysed can be clearly distinguished from each other in addition to the commonality of the funding line (Millis et al., 2010). With regard to the target countries of the IBB funding line programmes, the countries Kazakhstan (I_1), Iran (I_2, I_4), China (I_3), Serbia (I_5) and South Korea (I_6) are addressed. Furthermore, the vocational training programmes of the analysed projects include one project, which offers initial training (I_2) and five projects, which offer further vocational training (I_1, I_3, I_4, I_5, I_6). With regard to the economic sectors, different areas are addressed by the projects, so that sometimes even several sectors are addressed at the same time by one project. The projects thus address the following sectors: The automotive industry (I_4, I_6), metal and electrical engineering (I_5, I_6), tourism and gastronomy (I_5), environmental and energy technology (I_1), logistics and transport (I_1, I_5), Refrigeration and air-conditioning technology (I_2) and the industrial enterprises and manufacturing industry (I_3, I_5).

In total, four interviews were conducted in the area of practice-based research in the context of (international) vocational education and training research and service development with experts from four IBB projects, while interviews were conducted with experts from private vocational training companies in two other IBB projects. In our study, qualitative content analysis according to Kuckartz (2018) is used to analyse the results of the qualitative expert interviews. Our qualitative data are supplemented with quantitative data from an online survey completed 6 months after the end of the projects by the project participants.

4 Results and discussion

We found that the motivation varies from project to project, still, we see that the impulse to transfer or the motivation to become internationally active in the context of vocational education and training is related to the goals that the projects are primarily pursuing, which may provide initial indications of the underlying understanding of transfer of the projects (Meyne & Peters, 2022).

Although motives variate in many facets, we found two main motivations in our data (see Figure 1). Firstly, the revenue-oriented motivation of transfer can be emphasized in some projects: "We want to bring licenses to the market" (I_3, 9); "Yes, it is always about making money" (I_4, 105); coming along with a strategic corporate interest (such as cooperation and funding opportunities): "We've been doing international projects for many years, whether it's in China, in Vietnam, in Saudi Arabia, so from that point of view it's kind of corporate DNA" (I_6, 4). Secondly, we found the personal concerns motivation of transfer. For example, personal commitment was mentioned in a post-soviet project (I_1). Here, as well as in other projects, the actors' own personal employment- and educational biography plays a role to become active regarding the transfer of VET services: "So for me it was always clear, or I would say the red line in my professional biography is actually the occupation with other cultures, other countries, other approaches (...)" (I_2, 10). Following on from this, the subsequent question arises: Is there a perceived proximity (towards the target region or towards the field of educational transfer)? This is the main motivation in some other projects. Additional, in one project we found a mixture of both: The need to define segments to grow in (in international markets) combined with the management board's personal preference for a region (I_5).

Figure 1

Motivation to be active in transfer (own compilation)

Regarding the Relationships Motivation Theory by Deci and Ryan (2014), we find in the data that there is a connection between the *motivation* and the two aspects of *autonomy* and *competence* (see Deci & Ryan, 2014, p. 54) regarding transfer. So, missing autonomy is a disadvantage: "We were not dealing with private individuals, but with public institutions, which of course also depend on the government to a certain extent and cannot act in the way they might otherwise" (I_2, 17). In another context, if autonomy was given, the project succeeds to get further: "We have then acted independently of the project, because it was too cumbersome for us in parts or the self-interest is not so tangible within the project" (I_3, 24). If self-reliant, competent decisions are made in the target countries, this counts as a success as well: "They have sat in a very decisive position and also, so to speak, helped to make decisions or perhaps even made them independently" (I_2, 16). However, an open task for further research is to operationalize autonomy and competence in the context of the present study.

In Pilz and Li (2021, p. 19), the authors "revealed four main motives for the policy transfer: Donor aid, state capacity-building, company capacity-building, and trainer capacity-building". Here, we can see the main difference between policy transfer and the projects' transfer approaches: In the latter's motivation, all four main motives from Pilz and Li can be found within single projects and still, the motivation of transfer is to be reduced to two categories (revenue-oriented motivation and personal concerns motivation) regarding VET service providers at the micro level. Hence, the motivation shaped the definition of transfer, so that a connection between these two categories can be expected. The revenue-oriented definition means transfer to be "transfer as business model development" as well as "transfer as orientation towards customers and markets". As a normative leading motive to be active in transfer, all projects mention this as a subsidiary goal, they aim to be supportive: "We want to make sure that people are qualified and that they receive high-quality education" (I_5, 8).

Also, there is a tangible and conscious understanding of transfer, but still, there are rather intuitive and interest-driven motives for engaging in transfer on the part of internationally active VET providers. As we saw in our data, the project actors do have an understanding of transfer. Still, summing up, there is an understanding of transfer (How should it happen? With whom? When?) but an intuitive, interest-driven, unconscious development of this transfer takes place within learning processes during the project's phases. This finding underpins Barkirci and Pilz (2019), stating that international VET experts do not yet have a concrete understanding of the profession yet. In general, reflection on transferability and the target countries' needs always plays a role in this process.

5 Limitations and prospects

This paper represents a first contribution in the context of international vocational education and training research on the side of German VET providers who want to transfer their VET services from Germany as the origin country to another target country and asks about the motivation to become active in this regard. Although motives variate in many facets, the two main motivations of the revenue-oriented motivation of transfer and the personal concerns motivation can be found according to the analyzed data. Furthermore, it should be noted that there are rather intuitive and interest-driven motives for engaging in transfer on the side of the VET providers, which is why further research in this area would be desirable. Limitations of the present contribution result from the very special sample and the German perspective of the actors. Motivation, voluntariness and relationships were analyzed here by individuals of the respective IBB projects. Capturing the organizational level is a research desideratum for the future. Furthermore, the topic of the success of the transfer process as an outlook exists in combination with the understanding and motivation of the transfer. What if projects have a specific understanding of transfer and motivation to transfer that affect their project, so that a successful implementation is made more difficult or projects even have to be cancelled? Also, to be considered for future research projects would be the connection of motivation and legitimation in the context of funded projects, since at this point it can be expected that the framework conditions of externally funded projects have an impact on the articulation of underlying motivations for the implementation of the funded projects. This aspect is not expressed in the interviews and should therefore be addressed in the course of future research.

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